

Thermo-oxidative degradation of some common edible oils during frying

Anindita Banerjee, Santinath Ghosh and Mahua Ghosh*

Department of Chemical Technology, University College of Science & Technology, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : mahuag@gmail.com, mgchemtech@caluniv.ac.in Fax : 91-33-23519755

Manuscript received 25 August 2012, revised 28 September 2012, accepted 28 September 2012

Abstract : The present study includes the deterioration of four widely used frying oils in India, viz. soybean oil, sunflower oil, rice bran oil and palm olein oil during frying at higher temperature. The oil samples were heated at 180–190 °C for 24 h along with potato chips and fried oil samples were collected after every 4 h. Fresh oil was never added to the frying vessel. The oil quality parameters viz. acid value, iodine value, peroxide value, *p*-anisidine value, conjugated diene and conjugated triene were determined. The investigation revealed that soybean oil possesses the least thermal stability. Though palm olein oil showed a greater thermal stability than others but from nutritional point of view, because of its higher degree of saturation, it is less suitable for human health. Considering all the aspects, rice bran oil came out as best option in the choice of frying oil.

Keywords : Soybean oil, sunflower oil, rice bran oil, palm olein oil, deep-frying, potato chips.

Introduction

Carbohydrates, proteins, oils and fats are the three major classes of food constituents. In nutritional field, fats and oils have four major roles viz. they furnish twice the amount of energy (9 kcal/g) than carbohydrate and proteins (4 kcal/g), they are carriers of oil soluble vitamins, supplies essential fatty acids important for many of the physiological functions of human body and makes the food more palatable and delicate by adding taste, texture and good smell.

Of all the ways of utilization of oils, frying of foods is a common and popular process often utilized in the food industry due to its significant sale and vast quantity of products¹. Though in household practice the oil is subjected to a short period of heating and the changes that occur in the oil during this condition are considered favourable as this improves the organoleptic quality of the product. But the repeated use of frying oils as encountered in commercial practice can produce undesirable constituents which not only compromise the quality of food but also pose a potential hazard to human health and nutrition^{2,3}. During deep frying, the oil is exposed continuously or repeatedly to elevated temperatures in the presence of air and moisture, a number of chemical

reactions including thermal decomposition, oxidation, lipid peroxidation, hydrolysis, polymerization, cyclization and pyrolysis occur. The rate of these reactions is dependent on time and temperature. At typical frying temperatures in presence of air, lipid peroxidation reactions proceed very quickly to form hydroperoxides that undergo further decomposition to yield a wide variety of secondary lipid peroxidation products. As these reactions proceed, the nutritional quality of the frying oil changes and may eventually reach a point when it will no longer be possible to prepare quality fried products and therefore the oil at that point needs to be discarded. There is some evidence that highly oxidized and heated fats may have carcinogenic properties because of potentially toxic substances⁴⁻⁷. It has also been reported that the nutritional value of frying fats is affected by loss of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), which supplement the essential fatty acids requirement in human metabolism^{8,9}.

A great variety of fats and oils are used for frying, but the choice of oil is affected by different factors. On one side the factors are dealing with the availability and price of the vegetable oils and in another side it is the quality of the fried food and the nutritive value of the oil. Ultimately all the oils should guarantee high quality and tasty

food with regard to appearance, flavour or aroma, texture with mouth feeling. Another important factor is the nutritional assessment of the oil. The oil should have a high oxidative stability during usage, to guarantee a long shelf life in order to reduce the cost resulting repeated use of the frying oil in the process.

The choice of the oil for frying is based on its oxidative and thermal stability which are very important to maintain the quality of product. The objective of the present study was to assess the quality of four widely used frying oils in India, viz. soybean oil, sunflower oil, rice bran oil and palm olein oil and compared their stability at higher temperature.

Results and discussion

Many plant oils like soybean, palm, rice, olive, cottonseed, sesame, peanut and pimento possess appreciable amount of antioxidants. The content of antioxidant in the oils and the changes on heating was reported earlier¹⁰. According to that report antioxidant tocopherols in sunflower oil and sesame oil seem to disappear on heating while in soybean oil the percentage reduces. Particularly intense or prolong thermal treatment may be responsible for the loss of the natural antioxidant as they are relatively unstable. This shows that the efficiency of tocopherol is very weak on heating. The loss of tocopherol in soybean oil is reported as 32% and in sunflower oil 83%. Sitosterol and stigma sitoserols are found to be stable in almost all the oils except palm oil as the formation of stearic and palmitic acid increases on heating. Rice bran oil contains considerable amount of oryzanol even after degumming and refining.

The fatty acid composition of the four oils viz. soybean oil, sunflower oil, rice bran oil and palm olein oil is represented in Table 1. The oil quality parameters viz. acid value, iodine value, peroxide value, *p*-anisidine value,

conjugated diene and conjugated triene were determined for each of the four fresh oils as well as for the heated oil samples collected at every 4 h of heating.

Acid value, which is defined as the mg of potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the free carboxyl groups in 1 g of the sample, can be used to assess the qualitative degradation of vegetable oils. From Fig. 1, it is observed that the fresh soybean oil showed a slight higher acid value than rest of the three oils. But the oil sample collected after 24 h of heating showed a very high acid value

Fig. 1. Changes in acid value of the oil during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180–190 °C.

in case of soybean oil when compared with others. Palm olein oil showed the least changes in acid value. An increase in free fatty acid has been known to result from hydrolysis of triglycerides, triggered by infusion of moisture from the food into the oil and by its oxidation. However, determination of amount of free fatty acids gives about the idea of degradation but it is difficult to ensure that the increase in free fatty acids is due to oxidation or hydrolysis.

The iodine value, represented in Fig. 2, gives an indication about the extent of the unsaturation present in the oil molecule. During heat treatment, a progressive decrease in unsaturation was observed in all oils. This decrease can be attributed to the destruction of double bonds by oxidation, scission and polymerization.

In order to assess the oxidative changes in different oils during potato chips frying, peroxide value was deter-

Table 1. Fatty acid composition of oil samples used

Fatty acids (% w/w)	Oil samples			
	Soybean	Sunflower	Rice bran	Palm olein
Palmitic	10.1	6.2	15.1	40.4
Stearic	4.3	4.4	1.9	4.6
Oleic	24.2	16.5	43.7	42.9
Linoleic	54.1	72.4	37.6	11.7
Linolenic	7.3	0.5	1.7	0.4

Fig. 2. Changes in iodine value of the oil samples during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180-190 °C.

Fig. 3. Changes in peroxide value (in meq/kg) of the oil samples during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180-190 °C.

mined and presented in Fig. 3. Detection of peroxides gives the initial evidence of development of rancidity in unsaturated fats and oils. Significant differences were observed in peroxide value at different time intervals. The sunflower oils showed a greater change in peroxide value than the other oils. The palm olein oil showed the least change in peroxide value indicating a lower oxidation of the oil at elevated temperatures. This may be attributed by the lower degree of unsaturation present palm olein in comparison to other oils.

The *p*-anisidine value, which is a more reliable parameter to measure oil quality degradation with exposure

Fig. 4. Changes in *p*-anisidine values of the oil samples during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180-190 °C.

time, showed a higher reading in sunflower oil than other oils, as shown in Fig. 4. Here also we observed that the palm olein showed the least changes in *p*-anisidine value.

During the formation of hydroperoxides from unsaturated fatty acids conjugated dienes are typically produced, due to the rearrangement of the double bonds. The resulting conjugated dienes exhibit an intense absorption at 234 nm; similarly conjugated trienes absorb at 268 nm¹¹. An increase in UV absorption theoretically reflects the formation of primary oxidation products in fats and oils. Conjugated fatty acids as dienes were present in small quantities in all oils, as shown in Fig. 5. The

Fig. 5. Changes in conjugated diene (%) content of the oil samples during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180-190 °C.

highest levels of conjugated dienes were observed in soybean oil whereas the palm olein oil showed the least rise in conjugated dienes.

Conjugated trienes, which were initially present in all oils in traces, showed an increase with the increase in the hours of heating and is represented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Changes in conjugated triene content (%) of the oil samples during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180–190 °C.

Though, a large number of antioxidants are present in rice bran oil, yet it showed a higher value than the palm olein oil. The oryzanol content of rice bran oil was determined and the values are given in Table 2.

The foaming performance of the oils during frying as observed is given in the Table 3. The foaming tendency of the heated oils can be attributed to the formation of

polymers. As can be seen from the Table 3, foaming started at 24 h of heating in case of palm olein oil, whereas in case of soybean oil and sunflower oil it started at 12 h only. The reason may be due to dehydration products like enhanced formation of FFA and other polar compounds like oxidation products and also hydrolysis products like diglycerides, fatty acids etc. In case of the rice bran oil, the foaming started at 16 h. Though unsaturated fatty acids are present in rice bran oil in a good amount, but may be due to the presence of large number of antioxidants, foaming of the oil has been delayed.

All the above chemical analyses established that the soybean oil showed the most deterioration while the palm olein oil showed a much stable condition even after 24 h of heating.

Though the investigations demonstrated the excellent suitability of palm olein oil for its use as frying medium on account of its high oxidative stability, but because of its high content of saturated fatty acids, which is unfavourable from nutritional point of view, the choice of the oil needs a second thought. The saturated fatty acids like palmitic acid, together with lauric and myristic acid seems to have a negative influence on the formation of low-density lipoprotein (LDL)-cholesterol¹², while stearic acid appears to have a little effect on the LDL-cholesterol-rising potential of blood plasma¹³. From a nutritional point of view, soybean oil, sunflower oil and rice bran oil are more favourable than palm olein, because they consist of higher amounts of mono and polyunsaturated fatty acids and only low amounts of saturated fatty acids. Monounsaturated oleic acid is able to lower low density lipoprotein (LDL), while increasing high den-

Table 2. The oryzanol content (%) in rice bran oil samples during heating for 24 h at frying temperature of 180–190 °C

Oil	Heating time (h)						
	0	4	8	12	16	20	24
Rice bran oil	1.00±0.2	0.99±0.01	0.91±0.04	0.90±0.001	0.85±0.02	0.84±0.02	0.83±0.01

Values are expressed as mean ±S.E.M, n = 3

Table 3. Foaming performance during frying

Oil	Foaming starts at (h)	Excess foaming (h)
Soybean	12	16
Sunflower	12	16
Rice bran	16	20
Palm olein	24	-

sity lipoprotein (HDL), reducing the risk of cardiovascular diseases^{14,15}. But a strong disadvantage of these types of oils as frying medium is that the polyunsaturated fatty acids like linoleic or linolenic acid are susceptible to oxidation. Under the influence of heat and in the presence of oxygen and moisture, a fast degradation of these fatty

acids occurs. However, the rice bran oil contains considerable amount of oryzanol, the antioxidant property of which is found to be much effective on heating. In addition to it, cholesterol absorption from cholesterol-enriched diets and aortic fatty streaks have been reported for γ -oryzanol¹⁰. Therefore considering all the aspects, we can choose rice bran oil as an effective frying medium.

Our investigation revealed that soybean oil had the greatest thermal instability which can be attributed to the presence of linolenic acid. The linolenic, with three double bonds, is much more susceptible than oleic, with only one double bond. Linoleic has intermediate stability. This is the reason why high linolenic acid soybean oil seems to be non-satisfactory frying oil.

Experimental

Materials :

From local market, 1 L (910 g) each of refined soybean oil with brand name of 'Fortune' manufactured by Adani Wilmar Ltd., Haldia, India, refined sunflower oil, with brand name of 'Sundrop' manufactured by Corn Agro Ltd., Secunderabad, India, refined rice bran oil, with the brand name of 'Rice Gold' manufactured by Sethia Oils Ltd., Burdwan, India, were purchased. RBD Palm olein was supplied by Budge Budge Refinery Ltd., Budge Budge, India. All the oils were tested for their acid value and fatty acid composition at the laboratory.

Non-stick Nirlep Pan was used for carrying out the frying operations. Potatoes were purchased from local market. All the reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from E. Merck India Ltd.

Frying of potato chips :

The oil samples (1 L) were heated for 24 h as daily 8 h basis for 3 consecutive days. 200 g potato chips of equal dimension were fried twice for 5 min, once at the beginning of 8 h and other at the near end of 8 h. The temperature maintained during the whole experiment, including the frying operation, was within the range of 180–190 °C. The heating of the oil was carried out in Nirlep non-stick frying pan to prevent leaching from utensils. This is also to mention that neither salt nor any other spices were added during frying of the potato chips.

Oil samples :

Oil samples were collected after every 4 h and kept in

refrigeration. At the end of the frying process each day, the oil left was removed from the fryer, cooled under nitrogen and kept in refrigerator. Next day, the same process was repeated. Fresh oil was never added to the frying vessel for replenishment.

Oil analysis :

The oil quality parameters viz. acid value, iodine value, peroxide value, *p*-anisidine value, conjugated diene and conjugated triene were determined for fresh oil as well as for the heated oil samples collected every 4 h of heating.

For determination of acid value, iodine value, peroxide value and *p*-anisidine value, AOCS official method Te 1a-64, AOCS official method Cd 1b-87, AOCS official method Ja 8-87 and AOCS official method Cd 18-90 were followed respectively.

For determining conjugated diene and conjugated triene, sample weighing 0.0001 to 0.001 g was taken in a test tube and 10 ml of iso-octane was added to it. Absorbance was measured at 233 nm for determining conjugated diene and at 268 nm for determining conjugated triene [AOCS official method Ti 1a-64] by using spectrophotometer (UV-Vis Shimadzu 1700).

In case of rice bran oil, percentage of oryzanol was determined by spectrophotometer by measuring the absorbance at 315 nm¹⁶.

The foaming property of the oil samples during heating was also determined by eye estimation.

Statistical analysis :

All experiments were done in triplicate and the results were expressed as the mean value \pm S.E.M.

References

1. I. Sam Saguy and D. Dina, *J. Food Engineering*, 2003, **56**, 143.
2. H. Kaunitz, R. E. Johnson and L. Reagues, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 770.
3. C. Cuesta, F. J. Sanchez-Muniz, C. Garrido-Polonio, S. Lopez-Varela and R. Arroyo, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 1069.
4. P. R. Peacock and S. Beck, *Acta Unio. Intern. Contra. Cancrum*, 1951, **7**, 612.
5. A. H. Roffo, *Biol. Inst. Med. Expt. Estud. Cancer*, 1944, **21**, 1.
6. M. Sugai, L. A. Witting, M. Tsuchiyama and F. A. Kummerow, *Cancer Res.*, 1962, **22**, 510.
7. L. U. Thompson and R. Aust, *Can. Inst. Food Sc. Technol. J.*, 1983, **16**, 246.
8. S. Bergstrom, *Science*, 1972, **157**, 382.

9. J. Weeks, *Am. Rev. Pharmacol.*, 1972, **12**, 317.
10. S. R. Valantina and P. Neelamegam, *Res. J. Chem. Environ.*, 2012, **16**, 87.
11. F. Shahidi and U. N. Wanasundara, "Food Lipids : Chemistry, Nutrition and Biotechnology", Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 2002, pp. 465-487.
12. B. Matthaus, *Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol.*, 2007, **109**, 400.
13. B. F. Huamann, *Inform.*, 1998, **9**, 202.
14. M. Kratz, P. Cullen, F. Kannenberg, A. Kassner, M. Fobker, P. M. Abuja, G. Asmann and U. Wahrburg, *Eur. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 2002, **56**, 72.
15. E. A. Trautwein, D. Rieckhoff, A. Kunath-Rau and H. F. Erbersdobler, *Ann. Nutr. Metab.*, 1999, **43**, 159.
16. G. S. Seetharamaiah and J. V. Prabhakar, *J. Food Sci. and Tech.*, 1986, **23**, 270.